

TERMINOLOGY IN ARABIC LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides the necessary information about the history of the formation and development of terminology in the Arabic language, about the division of the lexical structure of the Arabic literary language into stages, about the translation of words that came from foreign languages into the native language in Arabic terminology, and the use of methods and tools unique to Arabic literary language.

Keywords: *Terminology, stages of development, “scientific terminology”, “morphological method” “الإشتقاق”*

INTRODUCTION

Terminology is the most relevant, extremely complex, theoretically and practically important branch of linguistics, that is, terminology. Terminology can be said to be closely related to all linguistic and non-linguistic fields.

The formation of terms is as old as the history of the people. In inscriptions such as Tonyukuk, Kultegin, Bilga Khakan, we find terms related to the crafts that our people are engaged in. They were also present in the folk legends and heroic songs. Mahmud Kashgari's work "Divanu Lugati-t-Turk", which embodied them, performed a great historical task in bringing them down to us.

The construction of bilingual and multilingual and explanatory dictionaries includes long periods. Dictionaries of Turkic languages began to be compiled in ancient times. M. Kashgari's "Divanu lugatit turk" (XI century), M. Zamakhshari's "Muqaddimatul adab" (XII century) and a number of other works are among them.

MAIN PARTS

It is known from history that the stages of development of the Arabic literary language, which unites all the Arab states and the Palestinian Authority in modern times, have not been the same and not uniform. It is accepted to divide the

development and formation of the vocabulary of the Arabic literary language into three. [1,17]

The first stage was associated with the emergence of Islam in the Arabian Peninsula from the 8th to the 12th century and the development of the Arabic-speaking Islamic civilization. During this period, Arabic literary language became the language of Muslim science, replacing Aramaic, Greek and Latin languages. In the traditional Muslim sciences (jurisprudence, history and linguistics), the basis of special nomenclature was formed by national terminology, while in the natural and exact sciences (chemistry, mathematics, geometry, astronomy) many Greek and Latin units were introduced through translation. A wide "network of special lexicon and terminology" was formed on the basis of the layer acquired from this foreign language. [1, 19]

The second stage (XIII-XVIII centuries) coincided with the complete disintegration of the Arab Caliphate and the period of foreign colonization. In this period, the development of the Arabic literary language was somewhat reduced, and some layers of the lexicon of the dialects entered the literary language. However, it was at this time that the Arabic language managed to bring many scientific achievements and cultural values to other languages of the world.

The third stage is associated with a new stage in the development of the Arabic literary language and, in particular, terminology, and coincided with the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. This period was directly related to the development of new Arabic literature, manifested in various genres, the growth of national self-awareness, the desire of Arab scientists to fully use the resources of the Arabic language, which is a means of spreading modern culture, science, technology and mass information. The comprehensive modernization of the Arabic language was caused by the political independence of the Arab countries and the implementation of deep political, economic and social reforms. Thus, Arabic literary language began to serve the real needs of modern Arab society in culture, politics, ideology, economy and other fields.

The classical and post-classical lexicon embodied in the literary experience of many centuries served as the foundation of modern Arabic literary language. According to F.M. Berezin, the author of the annotated dictionary of the Arabic language called "كتاب العين" ("Book of Ain"), which founded the scientific lexicography of the Arabs, is considered to be one of the founders of Arabic linguistics, Khalil ibn Akhmad. [2,16]

The most famous works on Arabic linguistics were created at the end of the 10th century and the beginning of the 11th century. Among them, Ibn Jinni's work

“الخصائص” (“Features”) is recognized as the most perfect work in Arabic linguistics. In it, the author considered the problems of the composition of words, variants, meanings of words, their use and other issues. Sa'alibi's work “فقه اللغة و انصار العربية” (“Linguistics and supporters of the Arabic language”) served as a special dictionary containing words borrowed from foreign languages, mainly from Persian.

The work of Ibn Faris, better known by the name “الصاحبي” (“friend /sakhaba(companion/)”), was devoted to the issues of classification of the original and adopted lexicon, homonymy, synonymy, monosemy, polysemy, as well as the formation of verbs and nouns. Al-Javaliky's “الموعرب من الكلم الاعجمي” (“Arabicized words from common/foreign/ speech”) and al-Khafaji's “شفاء الغليل فيما ورد في كلام العرب” (“Cure for quenching the thirst for the use of appropriations in Arab speech”) works of assimilated words. were as lists containing the causes and conditions of appropriation.

It is possible to cite the book “المظهر في علوم اللغة و أنواعها” (“Phenomena in Linguistics and Their Types”) by Jalaluddin as-Suyuti, dedicated to the problems of general Arabic linguistics in the Middle Ages. Akhmad Faris al-Shidyaq, Rifa' al-Takhtawi, Ibrahim al-Yaziji, Butrus al-Bustani, Sa'id al-Shartuni, Adib Ishaq contributed significantly to the development of the Arabic literary language of the new era and the arrangement of the original lexicon. [2,6]

Among the contemporary authors dedicated to the formation and development of Arabic terminology are Mustafa al-Shihabi's “المصطلحات العلمية في اللغة العربية في القديم” (“Scientific Terminology of the Arabic Language in the Past and Present”), Kamal Yusuf al-Khaja's “فلسفة اللغة” (“Language philosophy”), Husayn Mukhammad al-Khidra's “دراسة في اللغة و تأريخها” (“The Study of the Arabic Language and its History”), Jurji Zeidan's “تأريخ اللغة العربية” (“History of the Arabic Language”), Majid al-Mashat's “الدراسة المقارنة في تعليم اللغة العربية” (“About the role of comparative studies in the study of the Arabic language”) and the works of Muhammad Abdul Hamid Sa'ad and Ibrakhim Bukhayri “الدراسات اللغوية” (“Linguistic studies”) have a special place. Some issues of terminology are discussed by Sati al-Khusari “آراء و أحاديث في اللغة و الأدب” (“Thoughts and conversations about language and literature”) and Mahmud Taimur “معجم تيمور. الكبير في الألفاظ العامية” (“Dictionary of Taimur. The importance of dialect expressions”).

Generally speaking, Arab linguists first encountered the problem of standardization (harmonization) of scientific and technical terms in European languages during the emergence and gradual development of scientific terminology with the achievement of independence of the Arab countries. At the same time, Arabic linguists tried to use the internal (original) vocabulary of the Arabic language

as much as possible, to create their own term units through various linguistic methods instead of direct foreign language acquisitions.

When talking about the history of the development of terminology in the tradition of Arabic linguistics, it should be noted that there are seven Academies of the Arabic language working on issues of formation, standardization and unification of scientific terminology in Arab countries. For example, the Academy of Sciences, founded in 1919 in Damascus, Syria, has been publishing periodicals on terminological issues since 1921. In 1934, the Egyptian Arabic Academy was established, and in 1947, the Iraqi Academy of Sciences was established. Later, in 1976 - the Jordanian Academy of Sciences, in 1973 - the Tunisian Academy of Sciences, Arts and Letters, in 1993 - the Sudanese Academy of Sciences, and in 1994 the Arabic-language Palestinian Academy. Specialists in this field from Arab countries strive to unify Arabic terminology not only as a separate discipline, but also on an interdisciplinary, universal, and interlinguistic scale. In April 1961, an Arab interstate conference was held in Rabat, the capital of Morocco, dedicated to the solution of the issues of standardization and uniform systematization of scientific terminology that meets the requirements of the time.

The leading role of the Egyptian Academy of Arabic Language in bringing scientific terminology to a unified system and standardization is of particular note. This Academy was one of the first to apply the systematization of foreign language terminology using the kalka method.

For example, in the naming of measuring equipment, he proposed the model "مقياس الأبصار" - "optimeter", "مقياس القوة" - "dynamometer", "كلمة مقياس + موضوع القياس" etc. The Academy uses the Arabic "-graph", "-scope", "-form", "mono-", "multi-", "poly-" and other such suffixes in the European languages. Equivalents of "راسم", "تعدد/متعدد", "عديد", "وحييد", "شكل", "مجسم" were put into circulation.

"ورقي الشكل" - "sheet-like", "وحييد الخليّة" - "one-celled", "راسم التذبذب" - "oscillograph", "عديد الأذرع" - "polyarchy", "وحييد البذرة" - "one-seeded", "تعدد الأشكال" - Examples include "polymorphism" and many other terms.

However, despite the efforts of the Arabic language Academies to bring the terms of scientific, technical and other fields into a single system based on the internal resources of the language through the kalka method, there are also terms of direct appropriation in some professional areas.

For example, "ميكانيكا" - "mechanics", "استاتيكا" - "statics", "ديناميكا" - "dynamics", "ميكروسكوب" - "microscope", "ميكرومتر" - "micrometer", "كرونومتر" - "chronometer", "كمبيوتر" - "computer", etc. Such acquisitions were explained, first of all, by the difficulty in translating scientific and technical terms. In addition, the foreign

language option correctly and clearly expresses the intended meaning. On the other hand, the use of foreign language terms facilitates mutual understanding among specialists. But even in this case, linguists are trying to turn the acquired foreign language variants into "Arabized" half-faces. In the examples given below, half of the term consists of a foreign word, and the other half is an Arabic equivalent corresponding to this term: "عِلْمُ الدِّينَامِيكَا الهَوَائِيَّةُ" - "aerodynamics", "الدِّينَامِيكَا الحَرَارِيَّةُ" - "thermodynamics", "الإِسْتَاتِيكَا المَائِيَّةُ" - "hydrostatics" and others.

Despite the above-mentioned diversity and in some cases differences in terminology in Arabic terminology, the methods and tools that are unique to the Arabic literary language are usually used in the formation of new term units. The following methods of word formation are distinguished.

1. The morphological method of "الإِسْتِفْقَاقُ", that is, by adding suffixes, prefixes and infixes in accordance with the rules of word formation used in the Arabic literary language, and the morphological-syntactic method of "النَّحْتُ", that is, the formation of new term units using the addition of two or more independent bases ("رَأْسَمَالٌ" - "capital", "نِفْتُ وِغَازٍ" - "neftegaz", etc.);

2. Re-examining the meaning of the original lexicon, the expansion of the meaning - ("أُصُولٌ" - assets /main meaning - foundations, beginning), narrowing - ("سَنْدٌ" - promissory note; bond /main meaning - support, pillar/) and the functional shift of the meaning passing /shifting/ - ("كَسَادٌ" - kasod, kasod in trade and commerce, not walking / the main meaning - standing, stopping (about water)) is the formation of terms;

3. "النَّرْجَمَةُ" - formation of terms through literal translation of terms and combinations of terms in a foreign language ("عِلْمُ الإِجْتِمَاعِ" - literally "science of society", i.e., "sociology", "عِلْمُ الرُّمُوزِ" - literally "symbols science about", i.e. "semiology" and others);

4. "التَّعْرِيْبُ" process (i.e., "Arabization" - assimilation of words mastered using the types and models of word formation in the Arabic language) parallel to "الإِقْتِرَاضُ" - formation of terms by assimilation of foreign language elements ("بَنْكٌ" - "bank", "دِيْبِلُومَاسِيٌّ" - "diplomat" etc.).

By means of the first and second methods listed above, Arabic terminologists make wide use of the derivational possibilities of the language and create national terms instead of monosyllabic terms in a foreign language. V. M. Belkin said that creating new words based on existing models in the language is the most productive way to update the vocabulary of the language.

It should be mentioned that in some cases it is difficult to find suitable Arabic equivalents for terms that have entered circulation and become stagnant. This

situation is directly caused by the phenomenon of synonymy in the Arabic language and the regional differentiation of Arabic terminology: terminologists face the problem of choosing a single scientific term and introducing it into scientific and professional use.

The process of coining foreign language terms and bringing the resulting terms into a single system is one of the most urgent issues facing linguists. Currently, two-element (composite) term combinations are widely used, for example: “عِلْمُ الحَفْرِيَّتِ” - "science of fossils", i.e. "archeology", “عِلْمُ الجَرَائِمِ” - "science of bacteria", i.e. "bacteriology", “عِلْمُ الوَظَائِفِ” - "science of functions", i.e. "physiology”, “عِلْمُ الزَّلَازِلِ” - "science of earthquakes", i.e. "seismology”, “عِلْمُ الوَرَاثَةِ” - "science of descent", i.e. "genetics”, “عِلْمُ السُّكَّانِ” - "science about the population", i.e. "demography" and so on.

CONCLUSION

Arab linguists have tried to use the wide possibilities of word formation and internal vocabulary resources of the Arabic language as much as possible in order to form the national fund of the system of scientific terms. This approach made it possible to limit the acquisitions coming directly from the foreign language and to preserve the purity of the native language. When necessary, and in the process of transitioning to a unified system of terms, creating new terms through the kalka method also helps to save the Arabic language from the direct influence of foreign languages.

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